

Contemporary Practices Towards Business Excellence

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Abstract

Business excellence can be attained through best business practices. Business excellence can be attained through different ways but to select the suitable one is important in the modern competitive world. That doesn't mean by choosing the best business practice excellence can be achieved; but the chosen practice should be within the ethical limits of the business.

This article aims to examine the modern/contemporary business practices that can be adopted towards business excellence, and answers to the following queries in terms of business excellence.

While giving due care and importance to meet organizational goals what is the extent of ethics to be considered? What chaos arise when organizational goals comes in disagreement with employees' personal goals? What treatment should be given to employees who are fraudulent in his works towards the accomplishment of success and efficiency of the business? How the right employees can be recruited and motivate them to achieve excellence on their own?

Introduction

Any method, process, rules employed and procedures followed by a company in order to achieve its objectives can be termed as a business practice.

According to Bogan, C.E. & English, M.J. “Best practices are used to maintain quality as an alternative to mandatory legislated standards and can be based on self-assessment”

Bardach, Eugene says that, “Excessive optimism about the expected impact of untested smart practices is a common critique. If a current practice is known to be ineffective, implementing a promising alternative after weighing the alternatives may be worth the risk.”

In order to manage the firm as well as employees and attain best results firms do use certain values or concepts that can be explained as outstanding practices on which business excellence is often based. Later these practices have been developed as models for international organisations. These practices have undergone several changes, research, and extensive study of the practice and values of the world's highest performing organizations. Organizations used to amalgamate

the practices and principles and apply these models in their routine functioning and it leads to the attainment of benefits that business excellence brings.

Business Excellence Models

According to Business excellence tools, “Business excellence models are schemes or substructures which can be applied within the organisations and helps to concentrate on perceptions and operations in a more methodical and standardized way that should lead to increased production.

The models are comprehensive in that they concentrate on all areas and dimensions of an organization, and in particular, components that drive production. These are internationally recognized models as providing a schemes or substructures to help the adoption of business excellence principles, and an effective way of assessing how rigorous this adoption has been assimilated.”

“There exist several business excellence models. While variations exist, these models are all remarkably similar.” The most common include;

- “Baldrige (MBNQA) – Used in over 25 countries including US and NZ
- European Foundation for Quality Management (EFQM) – Used throughout Europe

Users of the EFQM Excellence Model, for instance, do so for the following purposes

Source: (business excellence.com)

- “Singapore Quality Award Model – Singapore”
- “Japan Quality Award Model – Japan”
- “Canadian Business Excellence Model – Canada”
- “Australian Business Excellence Framework (ABEF) – Australia.”

Business Excellence Frameworks

An organization can use a Business Excellence Framework to:

- Attain greater financial performance
- Create visionary and inspirational leadership
- Drive innovation in products and services
- Focus on customer service and satisfaction
- Increase market penetration and revenue
- Create effective business planning processes
- Raise productivity and reduce operating cost
- Engage teams in the process of enhancement and enlarge employee contentment.
- Develop resolution-making abilities and increase capacity to adopt change.
- Be acknowledged for your attainments in caliber and best practice.

Best Practices towards business excellence

1. Engross the employees

Isolated workers do not care about performing their own jobs. They give due care and importance to their rewards and interests. The very first thing a manager has to do is point out how to make his workers care about the company's objectives. Busy workers will be more passionate and high yielding; they will be less non-resistant, and takes up obligation for their productivity and allure fresh talent to the company.

2. Honour Effort and efficiency

None of the workers likes their work to go disguised. They feel appraised when they receive appreciation of effort and gratitude for a work well done. Often business management training overlooks the positive impact of approval. Some managers might even feel that being too "touchy-feely" undermines their authority. On the contrary, reward motivates employees to achieve more, work successfully and helps to build company constancy.

3. Be Committed

Trust among team members are essential devote a lot of time to avoiding conflict rather than airing their real opinions and working to find common ground. Staying committed to the team's initiative means creating an atmosphere where conflict is welcomed, not feared, because differing perspectives help to shape a clear goal.

4. Search for lucidity

Lack of sequence among managers is a problem with many companies, who either stop working to fulfil the company's vision or never understood what that vision was. Company's need to focus on alignment of core principles by asking the following six questions:

- Why do companies exist?
- How do companies behave?
- What companies should do?
- How will companies succeed?
- What is most important, right now for companies?
- Who must do what?

The company will lack purpose and direction without leaders developing and sharing a clear sense of the company's vision, its values, its strategic goals, and its delegation of responsibilities, the best business management education in the world won't matter.

5. Create Cultural Connectedness

Here, "culture" doesn't refer to ethnicity or socioeconomic status. It means a sense of shared values that, with the right level of engagement, will lead to the development of productive and efficient outcomes. Workers with shared values make good team members so that it is a good business management practice to make new recruits based on an alignment with the company's core values and its vision. In order to increase collective insight Diversity of race, gender, and socioeconomic status is a positive thing. Diversity in values can even lead to a company's downfall.

6. Hold Regular Meetings

In order to be fully successful, management should do the following

- Conduct separate meetings for strategic and tactical business planning.
- After the team has reviewed its progress against goals assess a tactical agenda.
- Enough time should be given for the clarification, debate, and resolution of major issues.
- Meet once in a month outside the work place to review what is happening in the industry, the company, and the team.

Conclusion

People might be tempted to think that ethics in business have been pushed to the curb while looking around at the latest news headlines, as far as modern business practices go. In certain well known undertaking it seems as though the headlines are full of businesses which have failed in the area of ethics. Some people may be tempted to think that like individuals seem to, companies can get away by having no moral code and still count on millions of dollars in profits every year. However, it is our contention, and it is still a belief among most successful small businesses, that modern business ethical practices in all areas are as important, if not more so, than ever before.

According to Ken Schramm “A smart person learns from his mistakes, but a truly wise person learns from the mistakes of others.”

The above statement can be converted in terms of business. An excellent business makes mistakes and so that the same will grow by adopting best business practices.

Accept the truths! Learn and improve! So that the business will grow consistently!

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